

RLUK Research Libraries UK

Technician Commitment Action Plan 2026-2028

October 2025

Overview

Research Libraries UK (RLUK) is a formal supporter of the Technician Commitment initiative.

Libraries, archives, and information institutions hold great technical skills and expertise. While the term ‘technician’ may not easily translate to the rich set of professional identities we celebrate within the research library community, we can readily identify the many diverse skills represented in academic and research libraries essential to producing new knowledge through research, innovation, and experimentation. These range from research data managers to archivists, from software developers to conservators, from photographers and makerspace managers to open access publishing professionals.

In our *The Library Transforming (2022-2025)* strategic plan, we pledged to work with our members to support and advocate for the library's role as active participants and leaders in the envisaging and undertaking of academic and scholarship research, utilising the unique skills and expertise library staff can bring to original scholarship, and using our diverse collections to enable and support diverse partnerships.

We have realised this through working with key partners to help build awareness of the value the library can bring to research projects, challenge perceptions of what the library's role can be, and providing financial and intellectual space for library staff to help develop transformational research skills.

With AHRC we created a **Research Engagement Programme (REP)**, with The National Archives we run a **Professional Fellowship Scheme**, and as a supporter of the Technician Commitment we surface the many diverse skills represented in academic and research libraries essential to producing new knowledge through research, innovation, and experimentation. Our partnership with AHRC has supported 19 AHRC-RLUK Fellows, and over 45 colleagues through our tailored our Research Catalyst Cohort programme.

The Technician Commitment aims to ensure visibility, recognition, career development and sustainability for technicians working in higher education and research, across all disciplines. We are a strong advocate of these values.

This Action Plan for 2026-28 provides a high-level overview of how RLUK continues to support the Technician Commitment for research libraries and allied and composite professions, including those working within archives, special collections across its four pillars.

RLUK and the Technician Commitment's Four Pillars

Visibility

The Technician Commitment highlights the need to ensure that technical expertise is recognised across organisations and that the contribution made by individuals is visible, recognised and celebrated.

Colleagues working across research libraries have a high level of technical expertise. These include archivists, conservators, and colleagues working to support learning, digital scholarship, digitisation, makerspaces and open access publishing. The range and variety of services and initiatives research library staff are involved in requires an increasing array of technical skills.

RLUK is committed to enhancing the visibility of the role that research libraries play in bringing their technical expertise to the research and innovation process.

RLUK will publish further case studies, illustrating the varied technical skills contained across our members and the contribution that research libraries make to the research process and the research lifecycle.

RLUK will continue to conduct wide ranging and original research into the ways in which libraries are home to diverse technical and specialist skills and the emerging opportunities to work collaboratively in this space, both nationally and internationally. This will build upon our successful AHRC-RLUK Research Engagement Programme (REP) through our Research Shift Programme which we launched in 2025.

RLUK will continue to convene its members around the core issues raised within the Technician Commitment, working with UKRI, AHRC, and key stakeholders, to further highlight and amplify the role of libraries as places of technical and specialist expertise, across a wide range of disciplines and professional practices. RLUK is part of the advisory board for the Careers and Skills for Data-driven Research (CaSDaR) Network+. CaSDaR is dedicated to enhancing the management, recognition, and reuse of research data across all academic disciplines and RLUK can ensure the voice and role of libraries is recognised.

Recognition

The Technician Commitment cites the need for technical professionals to receive recognition for their contribution to the research process. RLUK champions the pivotal contribution libraries make to the research process, as enablers, partners and pioneers of research excellence,

RLUK champions the pivotal contribution libraries make to the research process, as enablers, partners and pioneers of research excellence. This follows the publication of a [joint RLUK-AHRC scoping study](#) (June 2021) that highlighted that library staff are not always acknowledged for their contribution to the research process and that there is a need for greater recognition.

Our work strives to bring greater recognition to the wealth of expertise, skills and insight that libraries offer and to help support the professional development of colleagues looking to build their research capabilities and confidence.

In 2024 RLUK launched our [Libraries x Research](#) website to bring greater recognition to this range of initiatives and staff.

RLUK also launched the [Research Shift Programme \(RSP\)](#) in 2025 as a series of interconnected, interactive online events designed to empower and support librarians, archivists, information professionals, and colleagues across the Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAM) sector to actively engage in research.

It explores evolving role of librarians, archivists, information professionals, and GLAM sector colleagues as research leaders and partners. It will provide a platform to share experiences, develop ideas, and address challenges related to practitioner research.

The series is co-created with our AHRC-RLUK and The National Archives (TNA) Professional Practice Research Fellows and our Research Catalyst Cohort programme ensure it reflects the diversity of our roles.

RLUK is committed to supporting the enhanced recognition of research library staff as technical experts across a wide range of disciplines and professional practices.

RLUK will develop a Meaningful Measures toolkit to better measure and demonstrate the role of the research library, and its range of staff as part of its new 2026-30 strategy.

RLUK will continue to work with the AHRC, and other like-minded partners, to continue to highlight the contribution of library staff to the research process, whether as partners, leaders, or research support professionals, through blogs, case studies, and publications.

RLUK will continue to run its Research Shift Programme to develop a growing community of practitioners, mentors, technicians and researchers to further build their research capacity, capability and confidence across the sector.

Career Development

The Technician Commitment highlights the importance of career development opportunities for technical staff and the need for clear and documented career pathways.

Research libraries offer many diverse opportunities for career development and the continuous development of technical skills and expertise.

RLUK's Digital Shift Manifesto (May 2020) cited the need to continually support the development of technical and specialist skills amongst existing staff working across research libraries, whereas RLUK's research into *Covid-19 and the digital shift in action* highlighted the benefits of having a strong baseline of digital skills across institutions. The requirements of open access publishing, and open scholarship more broadly, require new technical infrastructures to enable the discovery, dissemination, and distribution of research outputs and materials. The need to invest in specialist and technical skill goes beyond digital skills, with the complex preservation requirements of diverse collections, and the curatorial need to present these to a wide variety of audiences, requiring the continued development of highly specialist, valuable, and technical skills.

In delivering these requirements, there are many collaborative opportunities between institutions, disciplines, and professional practices. Cross-institutional initiatives, such as the AHRC-RLUK Professional Practice Fellowships, the RLUK-TNA Professional Fellowship scheme, and the RLUK-AHRC Research Engagement Programme all support colleagues to develop their skills and expertise through a programme of collaborative knowledge exchange. Cross sector and international collaborative initiatives, such as the creation of a transatlantic data and digital scholarship skills exchange between RLUK and the Council of Library and Information Resources (CLIR), underline the shared challenges faced by research libraries in maintaining and developing their technical skills. Such initiatives also demonstrate the collective opportunities to collaborate in developing and sharing skills between institutions

RLUK will continue to support the career development of colleagues within its member libraries, and the wider academic library community, through its events, skills exchange, and fellowship programmes, research catalyst cohorts.

RLUK will work with its members to support new AI related roles and AI literacy

RLUK will work with AHRC, UKRI, and other like minded stakeholders to promote the importance of technical skills acquisition amongst research library professionals.

Sustainability

The Technician Commitment highlights the need to sustain technical skills across organisations and that these are fully utilised. Research libraries need to continue to attract a wide variety of complex skills and expertise to ensure they can continue to enable, partner in, and lead pioneering research, learning, and innovation. This will involve

attracting, and retaining, new talent into the sector whilst continuing to invest in the development of existing staff.

Research libraries operate within a shifting, international, technical skills landscape. An analysis of job descriptions undertaken in 2019/20 revealed the continuing diversification of technical and digital competencies across the research library community and that these feature prominently in job advertisements. Research suggests that these roles can sometimes be hard to fill and, in a highly competitive job market where technical expertise is at a premium, research libraries can sometimes struggle to attract and retain specialist technical talent.

As a result, research libraries often utilise a mixed economy of technical skills and expertise to support increasingly complex processes and techniques. They work closely with their academic partners, members of the postgraduate community, and third parties to access technical and specialist expertise around specific processes or techniques. They have developed internship and traineeship schemes, secondment programmes, and fellowship and scholarship opportunities as a means of diversifying the technical and specialist skills available to the library and to benefit from the expertise of a wider array of specialists.

This mixed economy has been seen to bring both benefits and disadvantages. It avoids the concentration of certain specialist technical skills within one or two roles, diversifying the pool on which the library can draw, but often means that its access to certain technical skills is transitory, associated with an individual project or programme. As the skills foundation of research libraries expands and shifts, new opportunities for collaborative skills sharing and acquisition will only become more important.

RLUK will continue to work with its national and international partners in exploring the changing skills needs of the research library community and the collaborative ways in which these can be met.

RLUK will produce and signpost resources for its members to use to identify their current and emerging skills needs, and to enable benchmarking between institutions.

Summary

Research libraries contain diverse technical and specialist skills which enable research, innovation, learning, and experimentation. As a result, RLUK endorses the principles and contents of the Technician Commitment and will continue to actively champion its application to the research library community.

RLUK will continue to encourage its member libraries to continue to engage with the Technician Commitment and to apply its contents to their own institution. RLUK will continue to convene its members around the key issues raised within the commitment and will advocate for the development, recognition, and elevation of those colleagues who make an essential contribution to the production of scholarly knowledge, innovation, and learning as Research Technical Professionals.